

12, 13a; R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=OMe, R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13b; R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13c; R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=OMe, R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13d; R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=OMe, R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13e; R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13f; R¹=R²=OMe, R³=R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13g; R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H
 12, 13h; R¹=R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=R⁶=H

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on Perkin-Elmer 577, Perkin-Elmer 720 and Beckmann ir-20 spectrophotometers, nmr spectra (CCl₄/CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JEOL D-300 spectrometer. Specific rotation was determined on polarimeter in CHCl₃.

1-Oxo-2-indanylbenzoates (12a-h): To an ethanolic solution of 11 (0.01–0.02 mol) which was dropwise neutralised with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) till pH 6.5, was added on ethanolic solution of 10 (0.01–0.02 mol) in one lot, and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to a solid residue. The two solid residues were mixed together, treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, washed with water and crystallised from an appropriate solvent to give 12 (Table 1). The 2,4-DNP derivatives of 12a–h were prepared in the usual way.

Indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins (13a-h): The ester (12a–h; 0.01 mol) was added in small lots to concentrated H₂SO₄ (15 ml; 90%) at 0–5°, care being taken to add the fresh lot only when the previous one had gone into solution. It was stirred for 3 h at 0–5° and left at room temperature for 40–50 h. The resulting deep red or deep green solution was poured over crushed ice, and the precipitated solid

was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, washed with water, dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent to give 13 (Table 2) as pale yellow to deep brown crystals.

Indeno[2,1-c]isoquinolin-5(6H)-ones (14): A solution of 13 (0.005 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia, aniline, ethylamine, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine for 4–6 h on a steam-bath and left overnight. Ethanol was then removed on a steam-bath, followed by removal of excess amine. The residue was filtered, thoroughly washed with a little HCl and water, dried and crystallised from an appropriate solvent to give 14 (Table 3).

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Synthesis of Bis(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-arylhydrazones

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MANY 2-substituted-amino derivatives of 1,3,4-oxadiazole possess various biological activities¹. Some bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are also reported as antimicrobial agents^{2,3}. Moreover, some Schiff bases of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have also shown remarkable antibacterial and antifungal activities⁴. All these facts led us to study the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of the title compounds. The compounds were prepared according to the sequence of reactions outlined in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, m.m.p. and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds showing characteristic bands at 1 280 (N=N=C), 1 500 (conjugated cyclic system C=N), 1 620 (C=N), 1 120 (C–O–C ether linkage), 3 340 (NH) and 820 cm⁻¹ (disubstituted benzene), supported the validity of the compounds.

The starting material dihydrazide (1) was prepared by the reaction of hydrazine hydrate on diethyl oxalate⁵.

Scheme 1

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-thiol (2) : It was prepared by cyclisation of 1 with carbon disulphide in alkaline medium⁸.

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-hydrazine (3)⁸ : To bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-thiol (0.1 mol) dissolved in ethanol (99%) was added hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.2 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. Excess solvent was then distilled off. The resulting solid separated out on cooling was filtered and recrystallised (68%), m.p. 193° (Found : N, 56.56. C₄H₈N₈O₂ requires : 56.80%).

Bis-(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-arylhydrazones (4) : A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95% ; 15–20 ml) and appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 80° for 4 h. The product was isolated and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE HYDRAZONES (4)^a

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₂	118	57
2.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	170	54
3.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	151	58
4.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₄	163	61
5.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₈ O ₂	146	58
6.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₄	149	55
7.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₄	178	59
8.	3-OCH ₃ -4-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₄	177	56
9.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₆	209	55
10.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₈ O ₆	184	56
11.	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	C ₂₄ H ₈ N ₈ O ₆	162	57
12.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂	148	62
13.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂	121	59
14.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₁₀ O ₂	158	60
15.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₁₀ O ₂	167	54

^aAll compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening : The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against

S. aureus and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Results and Discussion

Out of 15 compounds, 6 compounds were found to be active (zone of inhibition > 20 mm) against gram +ve bacteria *S. aureus* and 7 compounds active against gram -ve bacteria *E. coli*, and 3 compounds were active against both the species. Compounds having 4-methyl, 3,4-methylenedioxy and 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy substitutions were found to be active against both the species.

Out of seven compounds (Table 1, sl. nos. 1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 13 and 15) screened for antitubercular activity, none was found effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). Compounds having phenyl, 4-methyl and 4-nitro substitution were found to be active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹).

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Synthesis of 2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-arylthiazoles

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HETEROCYCLIC compounds containing pyrazolone¹ or thiazole² moiety are known to exhibit potent fungicidal activity and as a result of which the present study based on the synthesis of some new compounds having a pyrazolone ring through